

<https://eurosciencegateway.eu>

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D 1.2 Dissemination and exploitation plan

Outreach and dissemination with tailored communication and branding

Work Package 1

Technical References

<i>Project Acronym</i>	<i>ESG</i>
<i>Project Title</i>	<i>EuroScienceGateway</i>
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<i>Document</i>	<i>D 1.2 Dissemination and exploitation plan</i>
<i>Work Package</i>	<i>Work Package 1</i>
<i>Task</i>	<i>1.5 Outreach and dissemination with tailored communication and branding</i>
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Dissemination and exploitation plan

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* *PU = Public*

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (incl. the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (incl. the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. the Commission Services)

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Executive Summary

This document aims to identify, explain and plan the best communication tools that serve the purpose of dissemination and exploitation of the results of the EuroScienceGateway project.

The dissemination and exploitation plan will be developed in the first months of the project and execute a communication strategy, including: the development and update of the project website; a regular blog shared on the consortium website as well as through the channels of the consortium partners to reach out to all stakeholders, participation in user conferences, use of well established community channels in Twitter and other social media to share relevant news, use cases and other novelties, foster of community building by identifying and promoting user success stories, e.g. achievements and papers that have been enabled by EuroScienceGateway.

Dissemination and exploitation plan

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
BOF	B irds o f a F eather
D&E	D issemination & E xploitation
EB	E xecutive B oard
EOSC	E uropean O pen S cience C loud, a grouping of infrastructure services, projects, policies and institutions, mostly within EU, that aim to support researchers for achieving Open Science and FAIR ¹
ESG	E uro S cience G ateway (this project)
FAIR	F indable, A ccessible, I nteroperable, R eusable ² , a set of principles for scientific data management that emphasizes best practices and machine readability
GA	G eneral A ssembly
GTN	G alaxy T raining N etwork
KPI	K ey P erformance I ndicators
WP	W ork P ackage

¹ <https://www.eosc.eu>

² <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Dissemination and exploitation plan

1. Disambiguation: communication - dissemination - exploitation

A central goal of communication and dissemination is to maximize opportunities to promote, communicate and disseminate research results throughout the lifetime of EuroScienceGateway, and beyond. This will ensure that key stakeholders can contribute to, and act on the findings in a timely fashion.

Communication aims to reach out to the society, media and stakeholders to share activities and results widely with anyone and everyone interested in the project. Results are any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information. It demonstrates how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

For dissemination, knowledge and results are provided for others to use. Provision takes place e.g. in scientific papers, promotion at conferences, and makes data and workflows accessible in databases.

Exploitation means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including inter alia, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.

Finally, communication, dissemination as well as exploitation point to stakeholder engagement; while such activities could be carried out one-directional, the receptivity to stakeholders comments, knowledge, opinions, should be held up and considered for continuous integration into the project's development. Actively seeking such inputs, respecting and especially considering them in particular decision processes, is regarded to be crucial for receiving extended support and deeper insights into rapidly evolving scientific fields. Keeping up feedback loops with stakeholders supports the targeted adaptation to details or unforeseeable trends in the project's scope.

2. Description of the project

EuroScienceGateway aims to deliver a robust, scalable, seamlessly integrated open infrastructure for data-driven research, contributing an innovative and customizable service for EOSC that enables operational open and FAIR data and data processing, empowering European researchers to embrace the new digital age of science.

Dissemination and exploitation plan

3. Project objectives

The overall aim of the EuroScienceGateway is to achieve our shared vision of an open collaborative digital space for European scientists. EuroScienceGateway will deliver our vision through four specific project objectives, linked to measurable outcomes, that connect the work across the work packages and infrastructures:

Objective 1: Accessible e-Infrastructure resources for European scientists to enable pioneering data-driven research across scientific domains.

Objective 2: Support the varieties of analysis types and diverse usage patterns through efficient and smart job distribution to appropriate and sustainable infrastructures.

Objective 3: The application of FAIR principles to workflows and adoption of FAIR Digital Objects to stimulate reusable and reproducible research and enable the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

Objective 4: Adoption of EuroScienceGateway by researchers in diverse scientific disciplines.

4. Objectives of communication and this strategy document

The dissemination & exploitation (D&E) plan shows a structured procedure how the project will communicate outcomes and results to:

- draw the attention of national governments, regional authorities and other public and private around open infrastructure for data-driven research practices and consumption
- identify particular expectations among stakeholders and policy-makers
- attract the interest of potential partners and scientists to join the project
- enhance our reputation and visibility at local, national and international level

The D&E plan is a guideline for the project partners on how to communicate and disseminate their outcomes as well as a demonstration to the funders. The implementation of the D&E plan is followed by the lead of the project together with all WP leaders.

5. Scope of the communications strategy

Information about the project and its progress has an important impact on all scientific communities, politics and stakeholders. Implementation of the D&E plan is dependent on different target groups of the project. In chapter 6, target groups will be defined and their demands are explained.

6. Target groups and their demands

The project and its communication strategy targets different groups of people, institutions, stakeholders etc. These are separated into those who are addressed directly in the course of activities, as well as those who are to be regarded as indirect targets, experiencing advantages by the project without being addressed immediately. However, all these targets are subject to considerations and consequently listed in the following.

6.1. Direct target groups

European Scientists: Access to tools, workflows, storage, compute resources and data will enable breakthrough research across disciplines.

Users of public data: This project will facilitate making high quality, validated FAIR data and workflows, which is crucial for re-use by the scientific community.

EOSC network: EuroScienceGateway will contribute to the adoption of e.g. e-Infrastructures and FAIR publishing services of EOSC across domains, lowering the barrier for cross-disciplinary research. This project will increase the use and adoption of EOSC endorsed principles, standards and technologies, as defined by the research infrastructures and various EOSC-related projects.

6.2. Indirect target groups

Education system: The open and accessible EuroScienceGateway is suitable and intended to train and educate students and citizens. The ecosystem provides both specific tools and resources for training, as well as the ability to use the exact same system to perform research at scale.

Dissemination and exploitation plan

European funding agencies and policy-decision makers: Computing resources are used more efficiently, duplication of effort to port existing methodologies due to infrastructure limitations will be avoided and re-use of resources and technologies across scientific domains will be stimulated.

Infrastructure providers: Gain in users, increased degree of standardizations, improved connection with other providers/admins

7. Key messages & projected outcomes

ESG's central aim is to promote largely the democratization of data analysis. Co-operative approaches have largely gained importance in various scientific fields. While through platforms like Galaxy analysis tools and their application in workflows accessibility for often non-technical researchers has been increased, data itself, its metadata and results remain largely hidden or incompatible to each other. ESG addresses current short-comings as follows:

Communities: Onboarding of new scientific communities in the EuroScienceGateway ecosystem, demonstrated by new users and increased usage per user, and contribution of new tools, workflows, and resources to the EuroScienceGateway. Inclusion of the established network in proposals for innovative research projects of multiple disciplines, as well as EOSC-related infrastructure oriented and trans-national access to research infrastructure projects.

Scientific: Transform the way scientists create, share and exploit data and metadata (like workflows) resulting in higher quality research and more innovation.

Resource providers: Implementation of the middleware developed in this project by resource providers not part of the consortium.

Global: Alignment with similar American and Asia-Pacific initiatives. Building a global network of shared resources for all scientists.

Thus, the different target groups need to be informed in a tailored fashion, placing particular messages and applying dedicated channels (media, processes, actions), described in Table 1.

Table 1 - Target-specific messages to be placed and approaches to apply.

Target Audience	Message	Approach
European Scientists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of analysis tools, workflows, storage and compute resources 	Research conferences, website, social media, publications
Users of public data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of FAIR data and workflow principles 	Social media, engagement with Galaxy events, scientific journals
EOSC network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the role of e-Infrastructures and FAIR publishing services of EOSC across domains To lowering the barrier for cross-disciplinary research 	Workshops and round table discussions organized by the consortium
Education system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the open and accessible EuroScienceGateway as resource and platform, used to train and educate students and citizens 	Social media, website, leaflets, newsletter, press releases, high-level event, workshops, articles in non-specialised media
Funding-, policy-, decision makers and opinion leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase awareness of the role of the data infrastructures for scientists To inform on project outputs To engage in the emerging research data infrastructure 	Parliamentary research conference and high-level events, round table discussions, website, social media, press releases
Infrastructure providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To increase adoption of standards in research data processing 	Workshops and round table discussions organized by the consortium

8. Communication Channels and Tools

The communication and dissemination process entails the proactive communication from EuroScienceGateway with all organizations when articles/messages are ready to be disseminated.

Dissemination and exploitation plan

Online media platforms will be monitored to provide information on the numbers, sources, types of content and individuals/organizations that promote or disseminate project messages, allowing for optimisation and targeting of communication to ensure maximum outreach of news or results.

We recognise that the persons representing the organization in the project consortium are often not those responsible for communication within their organization. For that reason, as per Table 3, we will establish direct contact by collecting details of the people responsible for communication in each organization.

We address various channels to distribute contents, described in the following sections.

8.1. Branding

Visual identity of the project and the branding manual of the project is constantly created in collaboration with the EOSC Association.

Project Logo

The ESG logo (Figure 1) was created in a democratized process involving all partners with suggestions. The final logo is adapted from the EOSC logo showing the tight connection to it and being a part of EOSC. The logo will be used for all marketing and communication material.

Figure 1 - Logo of the EuroScienceGateway project

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Digital Starter Kit

The partners will be provided with a collection of digital contents for their ESG-related use, denoted as 'Starter Kit', made available as shared Google Drive folder:

Starter Kit provided by EOSC: [Starter Kit - Google Drive](#)³

Besides the project logo, the ESG has already developed or planned to develop branding material to use for the consortium:

- Templates (currently available or to develop)
 - [Presentation template](#) (Figure 2)
 - [Letterhead](#) (Figure 3)
 - H2020 Europe reporting and deliverables
 - Project poster
- Project roll-ups with ESG logo and partner logos (Figure 4)
- General [leaflets](#) and brochures (English and national languages; Figures 5 + 6)
 - about the ESG
 - about the Galaxy project
- General project website⁴ (in English)
- National project website (in national languages)
- Grant Agreement Number - partners are requested to use the project GA in all their external communication and dissemination materials, together with the emblem and the accompanying text of "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Europe program under grant agreement No. 101057388.

³ <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1ymmk13mtgua8nSSmXeJnWT43BME0Gb73>

⁴ <https://eurosciencegateway.eu>

Figure 2 - Presentation template with ESG logo

Dear Ms/Sir,

Sed ut perspiciatis, unde omnis iste natus error sit voluptatem accusantium doloremque laudantium, totam rem aperiam eaque ipsa, quae ab illo inventore veritatis et quasi architecto beatae vitae dicta sunt, explicabo. Nemo enim ipsam voluptatem, quia voluptas sit, aspernatur aut odit aut fugit, **sed quia consequuntur** magni dolores eos, qui ratione voluptatem sequi nesciunt, neque porro quisquam est, qui dolorem ipsum, quia dolor sit amet consectetur adipisci[n]g velit, sed quia non numquam [d] eius modi tempora inci[d]dunt, ut labore et dolore magnam aliquam quaerat voluptatem.

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Best regards,

Figure 3 - Letterhead/letter template

Figure 4 - Roll-ups 'ESG Partners' (left) and 'Galaxy Project' (right)

Dissemination and exploitation plan

Figure 5 - Example leaflet, front site

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Dissemination and exploitation plan

Title 1

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Title 3

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Figure 6 - Example leaflet, back site

How to acknowledge EU funding

All dissemination material will include information on the EU funding mechanism for EuroScienceGateway by (a) displaying the EU logo (Figure 7) and (b) using the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101057388”.

Funded by the European Union

**Funded by
the European Union**

Figure 7 - Logo displaying the funding mechanism

When displayed together with another logo, that of the EU has appropriate prominence.

8.2. Project website: EuroScienceGateway at Galaxy Community Hub

Central for ESG is its dedicated project website (Figures 8+9), hosted at the Galaxy Community Hub as a well-known, highly frequented web resource. An attractive, user-friendly implementation has been set up and is already online⁵. It meant to generically increase visibility of the project's outputs to all target audiences and the global Galaxy community. This website will be the main information resource of the project. Mutual links between the partners' websites redirect traffic to the project website; here, links to all project partners websites are aggregated.

The project website contains:

- details on project aims & objectives
- project activities and events
- partners
- news and blogs
- publications
- contact details
- social media links/buttons
- links to relevant project resources, e.g. Galaxy servers, training material

All partners will regularly publish blog posts in the news sections, presenting their activities and results. From here, all blog posts will be published on social media, newsletter, by other projects, etc... Workshops, conferences, and training courses will be announced in a dedicated event section.

⁵ <https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg>

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Project Summary

In the past decade, many scientific domains have been transformed into data-driven disciplines relying on the exchange and integration of internationally distributed data. Exploiting this data is still a laborious and largely manual task, prone to losses and errors, and increasingly specialized beyond most users technical capabilities. FAIR practices are encouraged but their adoption curve is steep. The needs for compute and data resources, tools, and application platforms are often domain-specific.

Many scientists struggle to navigate this intricate ecosystem. Generally, researchers do not possess the computing skills to effectively use the HPC or Cloud platforms they need. Thus, new approaches are needed to enable all researchers, with widely ranging digital skills, to efficiently use the diverse computational infrastructures available across Europe, for asynchronous and for interactive applications.

EuroScienceGateway will leverage a distributed computing network across 13 European countries, accessible via 6 national, user-friendly web portals, facilitating access to compute and storage infrastructures across Europe as well as to data, tools, workflows and services that can be customized to suit researchers' needs. At the heart of the proposal workflows will integrate with the EOSC-Core. Adoption, development and implementation of technologies to interoperate across services, will allow researchers to produce high-quality FAIR data, available to all in EOSC. Communities across disciplines -- Life Sciences, Climate and Biodiversity, Astrophysics, Materials science -- will demonstrate the bridge from EOSC's technical services to scientific analysis.

EuroScienceGateway will deliver a robust, scalable, seamlessly integrated open infrastructure for data-driven research, contributing an innovative and customizable service for EOSC that enables operational open and FAIR data and data processing, empowering European researchers to embrace the new digital age of science.

Objectives

<p>Objective 1</p> <p>Accessible e-Infrastructure resources for European scientists to enable pioneering data-driven research across scientific domains.</p>	<p>Objective 2</p> <p>Support the varieties of analysis types and diverse usage patterns through efficient and smart job distribution to appropriate and sustainable infrastructures.</p>	<p>Objective 3</p> <p>The application of FAIR principles to workflows and adoption of FAIR Digital Objects to stimulate reusable and reproducible research and enable the EOSC Interoperability Framework.</p>	<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Adoption of the EuroScienceGateway by researchers in diverse scientific disciplines.</p>
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Figure 8 - Screenshot of the homepage of the current ESG website (top view)

Dissemination and exploitation plan

Projects Part of ESG

Work Packages

Work Packages
EuroScienceGateway is organized into multiple work packages, each with its own focus.

Expected Results

<p>Pulsar Network</p> <p>A mature and tested (TRL-9) distributed compute network with demonstrated usage across at least 12 European partners.</p>	<p>ScienceGateways</p> <p>6 national Galaxy instances operational and proven by the scientific community with more than 100,000 users.</p>	<p>Communities</p> <p>Science Gateway with a custom set of tools and workflows for the Biodiversity/Climate, Materials Science and Astrophysics community.</p>	<p>FAIR data</p> <p>EOSC-catalogued FAIR data and workflows that can be found, consumed, created and published by users of the EuroScienceGateway, demonstrated for each of the 3 domain-specific use-cases.</p>
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Figure 9 - Screenshot of the homepage of the current ESG website (sequel)

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8.3. Blog Posts

The major and prioritized tool for the project will be blog posts. Blog posts describe outcomes and results, announcements, publications, or other relevant news from the EuroScienceGateway project. Blog posts can be marked with the EuroScienceGateway tag [#esg](#) or, more specifically, with the different work packages (e.g. [#esg-wp2](#)) to receive a collection of all outcomes and project results. These primary blog posts will be used to publish (secondarily) on other channels (e.g. social media, websites; compare subsequent sections) and to constantly update the audience about the project.

Sharing our news with other EU and EOSC projects (e.g. EOSC FAIR-EASE, EOSC4Cancer, AgroServ, BY-COVID, ELIXIR, EGI-ACE) facilitates updating the communities and the interconnection of projects and its members in a very efficient manner. This is done by grouping our blog posts and assigning them according to the relevance for other EU projects where ESG stakeholders are collaborating and/or are involved in. The collection of news items (blog posts) are sorted into categories (e.g. training, tools, publication, community) and assigned by relevance to the respective projects (comp. Figure 10). A newsletter with this very targeted and specific list of posts will be sent out every three months by WP1. Furthermore, these blog posts will be used as information resources for reporting to the funding agency and other stakeholders.

Server	IT security management of the University of Freiburg certified by TÜV SÜD	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Tool	AlphaFold now available in Galaxy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Training	[GTN news] New Tutorial: VGP assembly pipeline	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Tool	Genomic analysis on Galaxy using Azure CycleCloud	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Training	Complete human genome T2T-CHM13v2.0 available in Galaxy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Training	[GTN news] New Tutorial Feature: Choose Your Own Tutorial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Hardware	Towards a sustainable storage, enabling co-financing of public infrastructure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Community	Usegalaxy.eu has reached 50,000 registered users	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Figure 10 - Blog posts from the ESG website’s news section are collected in a central list by WP1, where contents are assigned accordingly to different projects and topics

To allow all ESG partners to easily contribute actively to this process, blog posts (Figure 11) are written and submitted to Github⁶ as markdown files, which is a common format in our scientific field. For members who are not familiar with the procedure, a guideline⁷ has been designed to support partners in disseminating the information.

⁶ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy-hub/tree/master/content/news>

⁷ <https://galaxyproject.org/hub/contributing>

Dissemination and exploitation plan

Introduction to the EuroScienceGateway project administration and project management

Work Package 1 of the EuroScienceGateway project

November 24, 2022

The first Work Package of the EuroScienceGateway project will cover all aspects of project administration and project management to ensure effective reporting, and achievement of the project aims.

The actions within WP1 will start at the beginning of the project, in September 2022 and they will end in month 36 of the project, August 2025. The work package, led by the University of Freiburg, will create a framework for the project management of the project, ensure its execution, by monitoring the management meetings of the project. Data management, risk management and a long-term sustainability model, will also be included in the scope of this work package. Last, but not least, a good communication, dissemination and exploitation plan will be prepared, to support the constant use of the projects' results and the connection with the other organizations, projects and initiatives under the same umbrella of developing European open infrastructure for fair data.

- WP2: Stimulate FAIR and reusable research with computational workflows
- WP3: Building a distributed compute network across Europe
- WP4: Building blocks for a sustainable operating model of the EuroScienceGateway
- WP5: Use-cases from early adopters to embrace Open Science best practices
 - Biodiversity
 - Astronomy
 - Climate Science
 - Material Science
 - New, yet unknown communities :)

Figure 11 - Example Blog Post⁸ for the introduction of WP1

8.4. Conferences and Round Tables

Organizing and attending scientific conferences will be a major effort to interactively communicate the mission of ESG as well as to disseminate outcomes and results of the different WPs. Technical outcomes as well as scientific and community outcomes will be presented and discussed at respective gatherings, meetings, and conferences in talks and poster presentations.

Round table discussions about more specific topics for a smaller target audience will be organized via e.g. a 'Birds of a feather' (BoF) format during meetings and conferences.

We will actively track those activities in an ESG-shared document with detailed information (see Table 5 - Dissemination activity tracking table) and write blog posts for the ESG website for further dissemination (see section 8.5).

8.5. Publications and Press Releases

Major results and scientific outcomes which are relevant for the audience will be published in scientific open access journals. We aim to have major collaboration

⁸ <https://galaxyproject.org/news/2022-11-24-esg-wp1>

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publications during the project run time from all ESG partners together, and publications from different partner sites for their own outcomes.

Press releases about outcomes and results are aimed to be published in national or local magazines for a general audience (e.g. university journals such as “uni’leben”⁹ from Freiburg or scientific ones, e.g. “Laborjournal”¹⁰), mainly via the editorial offices of ESG partner sites (e.g. university editorial staff) and connected umbrella organizations (e.g. de.NBI office, ELIXIR, EOSC).

We will track those activities in a ESG-shared document with detailed information (see Table 2: Publication activities tracking table) and write Blog posts for the ESG website for further dissemination (see section 8.3).

Table 2 - Publication activities tracking table (incl. one example entry)

Type of Publication	Partner site	Date [mm/yyyy]	Journal	Topic	Link
Blog Post	WP1	01/2023	online	ESG - Fairease, new community	https://fairease.eu/news/stronger-together-fair-ease-and-eurosciencegateway-join-forces

8.6. Additional Communication Channels

In addition to the EuroScienceGateway website and the blog posts, the project partners are already using established communication channels to disseminate their outcomes. The channels comprise majorly LinkedIn and Twitter, but also other platforms (comp. Table 3). News and blog posts relevant for the EuroScienceGateway project will be collected from the project partners, coordinated and published on <https://eurosciencegateway.eu> and from there distributed to partner websites, as well as on the listed further channels. Therefore, channel-specific adaptations might be introduced, like generating teasing texts plus links to blog posts (comp. preceding section).

To increase the visibility of the results and bring them to the attention of the other target groups, the blog posts will be regularly shared on the following channels mentioned below. Sharing the blog posts to other social media channels should become an automated process, which is in development. We are planning to democratize access to

⁹ https://kommunikation.uni-freiburg.de/the_media?set_language=en

¹⁰ <https://www.laborjournal.de>

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social media accounts and would like to introduce bots that can convert the primary blog source to tweets, toots etc.. This work is in process.

Twitter

All partners are invited to inform the public and share their outcomes and results with other scientists and stakeholders by posting news at least twice per month using the tags #eurosciencegateway and #usegalaxy.

LinkedIn

Reaching out to other scientists and stakeholders via LinkedIn will be done by posting news at least weekly using #eurosciencegateway and #usegalaxy.

Mastodon

Mastodon is more and more used as an alternative to Twitter. We use it to reach out to other scientists and stakeholders by posting news at least weekly using #eurosciencegateway and #usegalaxy.

Youtube

The Galaxy project has its own Youtube channel¹¹ to introduce the Galaxy project and disseminate e.g. training videos. Training videos contain hands-on instructions of the Galaxy Training Network¹² (GTN) materials or explanation of scientific topics. The Galaxy project has already published communication- and outreach videos about, e.g. the Galaxy community¹³ and the GTN. We will use this channel to help onboarding new communities and spread information about activities of the ESG as well.

Other channels

The EOSC Forum¹⁴ offers news sites where we will link relevant ESG content to share outcomes and news with all EOSC members.

The EU Horizon Results Platform¹⁵ will be used to disseminate key exploitation results.

Printed material will be limited because of environmental constraints. They can be produced, e.g. in the form of a bookmark and leaflet explaining the project objectives and outcomes in accessible language, for distribution by partners at relevant events.

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/c/galaxyproject>

¹² <https://youtu.be/IDqWxzWNk1k>

¹³ <https://youtu.be/-1MPdxmRs8U>

¹⁴ <https://forum.eosc.eu>

¹⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

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An introductory slide deck is provided to partners presenting the project consistently, mentioning the same objectives and activities, and using the same terminology and style.

An appealing and accessible bi-annual e-newsletter will be created and disseminated widely through the project's and partners' networks and communication channels. Therefore, relevant blog posts and e.g. upcoming events from/for the ESG project will be collected and sent as a news items list to relevant partners and stakeholders.

Table 3 - Available communication channels and tools in ESG, by project partner

#	Partner	PR & Communication contact	Partner Website	LinkedIn	Twitter	Other relevant channels
1	ALU FR	Anika Erxleben-Eggenhofer	https://galaxyproject.org/eu	https://www.linkedin.com/school/albert-ludwigs-universitaet-freiburg GalaxyProject https://www.linkedin.com/groups/4907635	https://twitter.com/galaxyproject	Galaxy Community Hub Mastodon https://bawü.social/@galaxyfreiburg
2	EGI	Magdalena Brus	https://www.egi.eu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/egi-foundation	https://twitter.com/egi_einfra	https://www.youtube.com/c/EGIFederation
3	CNR	Francesca De Leo	https://elixir-italy.org	https://it.linkedin.com/company/consiglio-nazionale-delle-ricerche	https://twitter.com/elixir_it	https://www.cnr.it/en
4	CNRS	Olivier Collin	https://www.genouest.org		https://twitter.com/GenOuest	
5	INFN	Stefano Nicotri	https://home.infn.it/it	https://www.linkedin.com/company/infn	https://twitter.com/infn	www.ba.infn.it
6	VIB	Alexander Halksworth	https://elixir-belgium.org	https://be.linkedin.com/company/elixir-belgium	https://twitter.com/ELIXIRnodeBE	
7	UP	Virginie His	https://apc.u-paris.fr/APC_CS	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universit%C3%A9-paris-cit%C3%A9/my	https://twitter.com/univ_paris_cite	

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				company		
8	BSC	Eva Alloza	https://www.bsc.es	https://www.linkedin.com/company/barcelona-supercomputing-center	http://twitter.com/bsc_cns	https://inb-elixir.es
9	UIO	Eivind Hovig Abdulrahman Azab	https://uio.no	https://no.linkedin.com/school/universitetet-i-oslo/	https://twitter.com/UniOslo	https://www.ous-research.no/hovig https://www.usit.uio.no/english/about/organisation/rde/scs/staff/azab
10	UB	Josep Ll. Gelpi	https://www.ub.edu	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-barcelona	https://twitter.com/UniBarcelona	
11	CESNET	Anna Filinova	https://www.cesnet.cz	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cesnet-z.s.p.o	https://twitter.com/CESNET_cz	
12	TUBITAK	Hakan Bayindir	https://ulakbim.tubitak.gov.tr	https://www.linkedin.com/in/tubitak-ulakbim-2803621a3	https://twitter.com/tubitakulakbim	
13	Cyfronet AGH	Lukasz Dutka	https://www.cyfronet.pl/en		https://twitter.com/Cyfronet	
14	IISAS	Viet Tran	https://www.ui.sav.sk/w/en	https://www.linkedin.com/company/institute-of-informatics-slovak-academy-of-sciences		
15	UNIMAN	Stian Soiland-Reyes	https://www.manchester.ac.uk	https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-manchester	https://twitter.com/OfficialUoM	https://esciencelab.org.uk

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					https://twitter.com/csmcr	
16	UKRI	Leandro Liborio	https://www.ukri.org	https://www.linkedin.com/company/uk-research-innovation	https://twitter.com/UKRI_News	https://muon-spectroscopy-computational-project.github.io
17	EPFL	Volodymyr Sevchenko	https://www.epfl.ch/en	https://www.linkedin.com/school/epfl	https://twitter.com/EPFL_en	https://www.scd.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/home.aspx

9. Exploitation

Outcomes and results will be used by the communities and new users. New tools, workflows, and training material will be made available via the Galaxy platform and the GTN.

Making our work accessible and usable, besides publications, we present the work at meetings and conferences. Visibility of the project as well as information exchange, presentation of outcomes and results will be enhanced by the co-location of ESG events. We will have mainly three different kinds of events for different target groups: hackathons, admin meetings and community conferences. While hackathons mainly address software developers, admin meetings are focussed on system administrators. Classically, these represent opposing forces (innovation vs. continuity); however, in practice these groups increasingly overlap (“DevOps”), even with normal users and in the same persons. Thus, the different meeting types rather focus on topics and principles than on real individual groups.

Over time, exploitation follows the high-level timeline displayed in Table 4, assigning the planned events to three phases (creating knowledge → consolidating networks → disseminating results).

Table 4 - Exploitation schema, chronologically.

Timeline	Purpose	Event
2023	Create knowledge	Hackathon (I)
		Admin Workshop, April 17th-21st, Belgium
		European Galaxy Days 2023, Germany
2024	Consolidate networks	Hackathon (II)
		Galaxy Community Conference 2024
		Joined EOSC conference
2025	Disseminate results	International conference / Symposium / EOSC - TBD
		Final Conference / European Galaxy Days

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Hackathons are targeted for working on common projects together, admin meetings are provided to discuss strategies, solve issues and support the project realization on the technical side. Community meetings bring together experts from similar scientific disciplines.

10. Monitoring and performance measures

Key elements in D&E are a constant monitoring of activities and mainly quantitative measures of the project's performance in order to ensure transparency and be able to provide rich and useful information.

10.1. Monitoring

Monitoring the progress of the project is fundamental for the success of the project. There are different regular meetings of project members. All meetings will be well documented using rolling minutes with a participants list, partner activities, progress, and actions to take, and are accessible to the whole consortium.

Relevant Project Meetings and their relevance to Communications

Meetings address different categories of project members, supporting concise and efficient exchange of information. ESG defines the following meetings:

Work packages (WPs)

Work packages have members of different partner sites and the meeting of each WP takes place monthly and has a status report character where members present current progress on the defined tasks and report issues. For each meeting, WPs will identify possible content for blog posts. WP1 is present at all WP meetings to check for fulfillment of tasks and correct execution of the meetings, and to answer organizational questions. WP meetings take place online.

Work Package Leaders

Work Package Leader meetings take place monthly and bring together all WP leads to exchange information about recent progress, outcomes, results, and problems. They regularly check the progress of the project and report deviations from the original plan. Regular communication workshops with the WP leaders will be organized to gather their inputs about the topics that would be worth to cover in blogs/social media, etc. or their needs in terms of user engagement (surveys, events, etc). WP Leaders meetings take place online and are collected every 3 months with the Executive Board meeting.

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Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board meets every 3 months to implement the actions decided by the General Assembly (GA) and to follow the progress and fulfillment of the timeline of the project. EB meetings take place online.

General Assembly (GA)

The yearly general assembly draws the overall outline of the project and adjusts deviations from the GA and CA. The representatives define directions of the project and resulting actions. This main meeting will be co-located with another conference and held as a hybrid meeting (in person/online).

Dissemination and exploitation activities are a fixed agenda item for Executive Board (EB) and General Assembly (GA) meetings to allow all partners to provide input on:

- The efficiency of the dissemination activities
- Identification of opportunities for dissemination activities (e.g. forthcoming events, calls for papers, etc.)

The communication manager, in consultation with the contributing partners, is responsible for developing an activity report, which will be reviewed by the ESG EB and the GA.

The reviewers will assess and give their feedback, including:

- Information delivered and visual appeal of the ESG website
- Activity and effectiveness of the ESG presence on social media
- Effectiveness of engagement with new stakeholders
- Visibility of ESG beyond the project consortium
- Quality, content, and effectiveness of the printed dissemination material

The EB and GA will also be asked to provide recommendations on:

- How to improve the impact of dissemination activities?
- Which actions need to be taken in order to enhance the dissemination activities?
- Where to put increased/decreased effort?

Reports on Communication Activities

Project partners will be required to fill in the table gathering information on their communications activities - such a table (see example Table 5) will not only serve for the reporting purposes, but also as a piece of information that could be further communicated to external stakeholders.

As blog posts will be tagged with #esg and the respective WP tags, a history of blog posts can be created easily and taken for tracking and reporting on those activities. In addition, we will track all activities on communication, dissemination, and exploitation in a document which is accessible by all partners and which is controlled by the WP leaders and the project coordination unit. As communication is a dedicated item on the agenda of EB and GA meetings, a regular check of continuous dissemination will be ensured.

Table 5 - Dissemination activity tracking table (incl. real-world examples)

Participant	Category of activity	Topic/Title of contribution presentation	Reference to document [URL]	Name of event and reference to activity	Date [YYYY-MM-DD]	Location	Type of audience	Estimated Reach [# people]	Related project result
WP5 members	Online training activity	User, Developer and Admin training		Galaxy Smörgåsbord 2023	2023-05-22 to 2023-05-26	online	Galay User Community	2000	Training Scientific Communities
WP2 members	Training activity at meeting	RO-Crate/Bio schemas		Open Science Festival 2023	2023-06-04 to 2023-06-05	Cologne, GER	Mixed Scientific Audience	100	RO-Crate
WP 1,2,3,4 members	Training activity at meeting	ESG presentation and outreach		ELIXIR All Hands	2023-06-05 to 2023-06-08	Dublin, IR	ELIXIR General Audience	40	Galaxy and Pulsar network

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WP1,4 members	Talk at conference	ESG presentation and outreach		EGI 2023	2023-06-19 to 2023-06-23	Poznan, PL	Bioinformatics Audience	200	Pulsar network and Metascheduler
WP5 members	Organise workshop	ESG presentation and outreach		PASC23	2023-06-26 to 2023-06-28	Davos, CH	Advanced Scientific Computing	100	Outreach to Scientific Communities
WP1	Talk at conference	Community meeting with users, admins and developers		GCC 2023	2023-07-10 to 2023-07-16	Brisbane, AUS	Galaxy User Community	200	Outreach to Scientific Communities

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The EuroScienceGateway project period is 01/09/2022 to 31/08/2025. During the project run time, two narrative progress reports have to be submitted to the EU (Table 6). The first one after 1 year, the second one at the end of the project. Both reports will be submitted by Work Package 1. Together with the narrative reports, financial reports need to be submitted by each partner at the same submission dates.

Table 6 - Requested reports

Report #	Month	Duration	Start	End
1	1-12	12 months	01/09/2022	31/08/2023
2	13-36	24 months	01/09/2023	31/08/2025

Besides reports, 11 deliverables will be delivered during the project run time through the EU portal by the partners (Table 7).

Table 7 - Deliverables to be submitted by ESG partners

#	# in WP	Name	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date [project month]
1	D1.1	EuroScienceGateway data management and contingency management plan	VIB	6
2	D1.2	Dissemination and exploitation plan	ALU-FR	6
3	D1.3	Final summary of EuroScienceGateway main achievements, impacts, key results, sustainability data management and exploitation plans	ALU-FR	36
4	D2.1	Reproducible FAIR Digital Objects for workflows	UNIMAN	24
5	D2.2	Publishing workflow enriched FDOs to EOSC	UNIMAN	30
6	D3.1	Operations documentation on the Open Infrastructure deployment	INFN	24
9	D3.2	Publication on the Pulsar Network, integrated in workflow management systems	CNR	36
7	D4.1	Bring Your Own Infrastructure (compute,	EGI-Foundation	24

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		storage) Demonstrator		
8	D4.2	Publication on the smart job scheduler implementation	EGI-Foundation	30
D10	D5.1	Community onboarding cookbook published	UiO	18
D11	D5.2	Publication of the usage of EuroScienceGateway by multiple communities	UiO	36

In addition to EU-requested reports, some partner sites have internal periodic reports for their stakeholders to share information. ALU-FR for example shares yearly [reports](#) to local and national stakeholders about recent statistics, new Galaxy features, news and upcoming events.

10.2. Performance measures

To measure the performance of ESG and keep track of key performance indicators (KPI's), we will expose aggregated statistics about tools and resource usage, the amount of users registered and how many users are using the Gateway in real-time. For this, we have set up a live dashboard at <https://stats.usegalaxy.eu> (comp. Figure 11). This website will also serve as a monitoring website for our system administrators, including automatic notifications, if a KPI has reached a new milestone.

The statistics page is built with the TIG (Telegraf, InfluxDB and Grafana) stack and therefore uses standard open source components that are also built into our open infrastructure deployments. The graphical component (Grafana) is modular, and we will add many representations and charts to visualize data from the ESG. For example, we are planning to have an EU map with an indicator of how many jobs are processed in which country in real-time.

Figure 11 - Example plots for KPI monitoring, as used on <https://stats.usegalaxy.eu>

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The real-time charts can be embedded into other websites and provide constantly up to date numbers and monitoring services for whoever needs them. Numbers from the live dashboard can be taken by the entire community to create other visualizations or update slides with recent numbers. We as WP1 will do so semi-automatically for our branding materials and slide decks. One example is the factsheet as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Factsheet (from Feb 2023) about the European Galaxy Project, which can be updated and modified for e.g. national Galaxy instances

11. Final remarks

The EuroScienceGateway is part of the global Galaxy project, which is already a fundamental pillar of many existing infrastructure projects. We are reusing the communication channels that have been built up over 17 years now, enriching them with community-specific channels and adding high quality EOSC branding material to the mix. It is projected that at the end of ESG we will reach more than 100.000 users using EOSC infrastructure.